

Nitrogen recovery from anaerobically digested blackwaters using Bioelectrochemical systems

E. Borràs,* D. Molognoni,* M. Aliaguilla,* P. Bosch-Jimenez,* M. P. Bernicola,* J. García-Montaña,* S. Sanchis*

* LEITAT Technological Center, c/ de la Innovació 2, Terrassa (Barcelona, Spain)

eborras@leitat.org, dmolognoni@leitat.org, maliaguilla@leitat.org, pbosch@leitat.org, mpbernicola@leitat.org, jgarcia@leitat.org, ssanchis@leitat.org

Abstract: The present work reports the latest developments carried out in the Run4Life project for the recovery of NH_4^+ by bioelectrochemical systems for the direct production of fertilizers from anaerobically digested blackwaters. On the one hand, the adaptation of an electroactive anodic biofilm to high concentrations of n-NH_4^+ is presented, as well as the inhibition causes. The selection of the most appropriate cation exchange membrane is also summarized, according to electric resistance and permselectivity criteria. Finally, the design and construction of an air-diffusion-cathode BES reactor for N-recovery trials is also presented.

Keywords: Nitrogen recovery; Bioelectrochemical systems; air-diffusion cathodes, cation exchange membranes

Session: Nutrient removal/recovery linked to AD

Introduction

The Run4Life project¹ aims at implementing new sanitation concepts to achieve complete NPK nutrients recovery from source-separated wastewater. A specific task is dedicated to NH_4^+ recovery from BW streams, previously treated by anaerobic membrane biologic reactor (AnMBR). Source separation of domestic wastewater is one of the pillars of the “new sanitation” paradigm (Graaf and van Hell, 2014), resulting in highly concentrated black water (BW) streams from the toilet, which can be efficiently treated through anaerobic systems like Upflow Anaerobic Sludge Blanket. Main benefits of such an approach include the possibility to recover energy from wastewater and micropollutants removal. On the other hand, anaerobic treatment does not allow removing nutrients at a significant rate. Bioelectrochemical systems (BES) can be used to recover ammonium (NH_4^+) from BW through the migration ionic flux occurring from anode to cathode chamber (Ledezma et al., 2015). The ammonium flux is driven by the exoelectrogenic degradation of organic matter at the anode, and takes place in both microbial fuel cells (MFC) and microbial electrolysis cells (MEC). The main advantage

¹ <http://run4life-project.eu/>

of NH_4^+ extraction using a cation exchange membrane (CEM) is that it allows the coupling of an extraction unit as the catholyte stream has low impurities. Problems related to CEM fouling and scaling have to be tackled when considering long-term operation using real effluents with high solid concentrations.

Several challenges must be tackled before N-recovery technologies based on BES reach the market. Within them: (i) adapting the anodic biofilm to high ammonium concentrations; (i) selecting the best performing CEM for recovering selectively NH_4^+ under real operating conditions and (iii) optimize the operating conditions.

Material and Methods

The experimental set-up for acclimatising consisted in 2 different air-cathode flat plate Microbial Fuel Cells (MFC). Biomass from a running MFC, operating at low nitrogen concentrations, was used as inoculum. MFCs were fed with an acetate-based synthetic medium doped at increasing levels of NH_4^+ , until reaching an inhibitory threshold. Both MFCs were electrically operated in chronoamperometric mode, while polarization curves and cyclic voltammetry analyses were performed at regular base (weekly). Physical-chemical parameters of influent and effluent streams were analysed by Standard Methods (in terms of pH, conductivity, solids, nitrogen concentration –total and NH_4^+ - and organic matter). So that process parameters, like treatment efficiency and Coulombic efficiency (CE), could be estimated over time.

Figure 1 Air-cathode MFCs used for determining inhibitory concentration of nitrogen.

The best performing cation exchange membranes were selected among different commercial ones according to pH tolerance, mechanical resistance, membrane electric resistance and permselectivity towards NH_4^+ cation. These two latter parameters were directly measured, in a tailor made set-up, in order to determine the CEMS performance baseline. A tailor made BES reactor was designed and constructed for the nitrogen recovery trials based on the use of an air-diffusion cathode and an acid trap for the direct recovery of a direct fertilizer (see Figure 2). The reactor was designed in order to be employed either as a Microbial Fuel cell or a Microbial Electrolysis Cell.

Figure 2 Diagram of N-recovery BES reactor (above) and the experimental set-up (bottom).

Results and Conclusions

One MFC was acclimated at a constant concentration of $0.5 \text{ g N-NH}_4^+ \text{ L}^{-1}$ (estimated nitrogen content of AnMBR-treated BW), reaching stable performances over a period of more than 6 months: average current of 0.7 A m^{-2} , 83% COD removal and 12% CE. The other MFC was employed to determine the NH_4^+ -inhibitory threshold by weekly increase steps of $0.5 \text{ g NH}_4^+ \text{ L}^{-1}$, looking for the critical value causing biofilm inhibition (Nam et al 2010). A notable value of $9.0 \text{ g N-NH}_4^+ \text{ L}^{-1}$ (equal to 0.9 g L^{-1} of free N-NH_3 , according to pH and temperature), without adverse effects towards BES performance. Current density decreased when increasing nitrogen content, while COD removal remained on values around 80% and CE up to 16%. It was demonstrated that inhibition of the electroactive biofilm was due to the increase of nitrogen content rather than increase in conductivity (final conductivity at $9.5 \text{ g N-NH}_4^+ \text{ L}^{-1}$ was around 80 mS/cm). Further experiments are ongoing in order to validate the acclimation to real blackwater effluents.

Figure 2. Current generated by the anodic biofilm and increase in NH_4^+ concentration evolution over time.

As regards to the selection of the best performing CEM, among 6 tested membranes, a candidate was selected due to the low electric resistance ($<100 \Omega \text{cm}^2$) and high permselectivity ($>93\%$) determined under N-recovery tested conditions. The ongoing stage of the study is focus on nitrogen recovery optimization from BW in a double-chamber air-diffusion-cathode BES inoculated with the acclimated biofilm.

Acknowledgements

Authors would like to acknowledge the EU H2020 Run4Life Project (2017-2021, GA 730285) for supporting the research.

References

- R. de Graaf and A. J. van Hell (2014). New Sanitation Noorderhoek, Sneek. P. Hermans. Amersfoort, STOWA: 304.
- P. Ledezma, P. Kuntke, C. J. N. Buisman, J. Keller and S. Freguia, Trends Biotechnol., 2015, 33, 214–220.